

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

M. V. Xalimova

O'SPRINLIK DAVRIDA MUSTAQIL KASBIY MALAKALARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA

BILISH JARAYONLARINING O'RNI

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/APREL

